

Agro2Circular

D1.4 – A2C Residues Management Plan (Final)

30 Sep 2024

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List of abbreviations

A2C - Agro2Circular

LER - European Waste List

DI - Waste Identification Document

1 Introduction

This deliverable (D1.4) is part of the A2C Project (Advanced Approaches for Circularity), which aims to promote circular economy strategies and improve waste management processes in the food and agricultural sectors. The general objective of A2C is to develop integrated, sustainable solutions for the handling, treatment, and valorization of various types of waste—particularly those originating from food packaging, agricultural plastics, and organic matter.

D1.4 is produced within the framework of Work Package 1: Waste Characterization and Management Practices, and more specifically, it is the result of Task T1.4: A2C residues management and preliminary characterisation. It connects directly with related deliverables focused on waste traceability, treatment technologies, and circular economy models, contributing practical guidance to complement technical and regulatory analyses delivered in other WPs.

The nature of this document is mainly applied and procedural. It does not aim to provide a state-of-the-art scientific review, nor does it generate new experimental knowledge. Instead, it compiles and adapts existing good practices for the practical implementation of waste management systems in real-world contexts—particularly for multilayer aseptic packaging, agricultural padding, and organic waste. It defines operational steps, hygiene requirements, traceability procedures, and legal considerations for managing these waste streams efficiently and safely.

The target audience includes waste management companies, food industry operators, agricultural cooperatives, public authorities, environmental regulators, and logistics providers involved in the collection, transport, and treatment of waste. The document is also relevant to organizations developing or implementing sustainability and circular economy policies.

Regarding its limitations, D1.4 focuses exclusively on waste types classified under specific LER codes, and it does not address treatment technologies in detail, nor does it cover the

full range of regulatory variations across all EU member states. Instead, it provides a framework based on current EU legislation and widely accepted best practices, with the understanding that national adaptations may be required.

2 Deliverable Body

2.1 Management of multilayer aseptic packaging.

2.1.1 IDENTIFICATION OF THE WASTE

Multilayer aseptic packaging is mixed waste generated from industrial activities in the food sector. It is not classified as hazardous waste based on its origin and composition; therefore, it must be managed as non-hazardous waste.

WASTE	LER CODE	DESCRIPTION
Multilayer aseptic packaging	15 01 06	Mixed packaging [including packaging waste from municipal selective collection]

Figure 1. Waste definition. Multilayer Aseptic Bag

2.1.2 ACTIVITIES INCLUDED IN MANAGEMENT

The procedure is summarized in the following flowchart:

Figure 2. Management of Multilayer aseptic bag waste. Flowchart

V*: Valorization

R12*: Pre-conditioning prior to recovery (fragments without aluminum from Demonstrator 1).

R3*: Recovery of organic substances not used as solvents (Demonstrator 7). For the plugs removed during the initial storage phase, an external manager is responsible for collection and recovery.

R13*: Intermediate operations aimed at recovery (subproducts obtained from the delamination process of Demonstrator 1).

19 12 07*: Waste wood from broken pallets, with recovery activity classified as R3, carried out by an external manager contracted by the generator of this waste.

07 01 99*: Waste from Material Conditioning (Caps), with recovery activity classified as R3, carried out by an external manager contracted by the generator of this waste.

E.M*: External Manager External Manager to the A2C project that valorizes this type of materials

2.1.2.1 INITIAL STORAGE and Good Practice Guidelines

Initial conditioning and storage must be carried out at the facilities of the waste-generating company. This process is crucial to ensure that the material is properly stored and preserved until treatment. The storage must be conducted under optimal hygiene and control conditions, as the final recovery treatment aims for application in the food industry.

Figure 3. Bag in box as it is used in the agrifood industry

INSTALLATION AREAS:

- Unloading and Acceptance-Rejection Area

- Conditioning Area
- Storage Area for Multilayer Plastic Waste

EQUIPMENT:

- Unloading and Internal Transport Equipment
- Cleaning Equipment
- Equipment Necessary for Removing Caps from the Material

PERSONNEL:

- The personnel assigned to this plant are from the waste-generating group, in this case: MOCITOS, LABORATORIOS ALMOND SL and CITROMIL SL.

A. GOOD PRACTICE GUIDE FOR INITIAL STORAGE

- **Location**

The storage area must be clean, free from contaminants, and separated from other waste. A specific zone should be designated for the storage of multilayer aseptic packaging, clearly marked and secured.

- **Environmental Conditions**

Maintain the storage area at a moderate temperature to prevent material degradation.

- **Material Conditioning**

Waste must be pre-conditioned before storage. Caps should be removed, and the rest of the material cleaned to eliminate impurities and organic matter, which can cause issues in subsequent treatments due to high glucose content.

The cap will be treated by an external manager according to recovery operation R3 (Recovery of organic substances not used as solvents).

- **Protection and Packaging**

- Waste should be stored in appropriate drums or containers, using protective and sealed covers to prevent external contamination.

- Pallets should be used to elevate containers off the ground and prevent contact with moisture or dirt. This way, any leaks can be easily traced back to their source. Additionally, it is recommended to use leak retention trays.
- Waste should be stored temporarily, never exceeding six months from the time the container is full, in compliance with the relevant packaging regulations.

- **Identification and Registration**

- Each container must be correctly identified with a waste identification label. The label must include the following minimum information:
 - ✓ **Non-Hazardous Waste:** Indicates that the waste does not possess characteristics that classify it as hazardous.
 - ✓ **Waste:** Specifies the name of the waste → Multilayer aseptic packaging waste.
 - ✓ **LER Code:** The code from the European Waste List (LER) → 15 01 06.
 - ✓ **Description:** Provides a brief description according to the LER code → Mixed packaging [including packaging waste from municipal selective collection].
 - ✓ **Producer:** Name of the entity or company that generated the waste. This is important for maintaining material traceability.
 - ✓ **Address:** Physical location of the waste producer, necessary for any inquiries or management related to the material.
 - ✓ **Start Date of Packaging:** The date on which the waste begins to be packaged, marking the start of its storage. This date is crucial for managing storage time and material rotation. It should not be confused with the date when the packaging is completed; only the date when packaging of the material begins is recorded. The packaging dates and batch number help deduce the waste generation dates over time.
 - ✓ **Batch:** A unique number identifying the set of waste, facilitating tracking and control from generation to treatment. The batch number is progressive throughout the year and follows the format of year and sequence, e.g., 01/24 for the first batch of 2024, 02/24 for the second batch of the same year, and so on.

- Maintaining an updated inventory record of stored waste is essential. This will be managed using the digital platform developed in the project.
- It is necessary to keep track of the locations of each batch using a map or a location system. Logistics should follow an order that facilitates easy access to the oldest batches, ensuring that these lots are the first to be removed and sent to the managing entity, thus avoiding unnecessary accumulations and optimizing the material's outflow.

2.1.2.2 COLLECTION AND TRANSPORT and Good Practice Guidelines

Once the material has been properly stored, the collection and transport process begins, coordinated with production cycles to avoid excessive waste accumulation.

This activity must be carried out using authorized vehicles and under conditions that ensure the waste is not mishandled or contaminated during transit. Additionally, transportation will be accompanied by a Waste Identification Document (DI), which specifies the type of waste being transported, the producer of that waste, the transporter, and the waste manager.

INSTALLATION AREAS:

- Loading Area at the waste generator's facilities
- Unloading Area at the manager's facilities

EQUIPMENT:

- Internal Transport Equipment for loading and unloading
- Authorized Vehicles

PERSONNEL:

- Transporter: In this case, GREEN WORLD COMPOUNDING SL will handle the activity, as it has contracted an authorized logistics company for waste management.
- Loading Personnel (Generator): MOCITOS, LABORATORIOS ALMOND SL, and CITROMIL SL.

- Unloading Personnel (Manager): GREEN WORLD COMPOUNDING SL.

B. GOOD PRACTICES FOR COLLECTION AND TRANSPORT

- **Coordination**

Establish a collection plan coordinated with production cycles to avoid waste accumulation. Notify the transport company in advance about the quantity and type of waste to be collected.

- **Transport Conditions**

Use authorized vehicles exclusively for waste transport to prevent cross-contamination. Ensure that vehicles are clean, disinfected, and properly sealed to protect the waste from external agents. All authorized vehicles must comply with and maintain a record of regular cleaning.

Waste should be transported in closed and correctly labelled containers. It is also advisable to load the oldest waste batches first to prevent potential degradation or bacterial proliferation due to the presence of organic matter. This could hinder processability or affect the final quality of the recovered product.

- **Documentation**

Accompany the transport with the appropriate documentation, including the Waste Identification Document and records of the vehicle's cleaning status. The format for the Waste Identification Document is included in the technological platform of the A2C project.

The minimum information that must be included in the Waste Identification Document is as follows according to the attached model in Annex A:

- ✓ Type of Waste: Hazardous; Non-hazardous
- ✓ LER Code
- ✓ Document Number
- ✓ Business Name of the Transport Operator
- ✓ Business Name of the Origin Center
- ✓ Business Name of the Destination

- ✓ Transporter Details: Name, license plate number, contact information, and registration number in the transporter registry.
- ✓ Collection and Receipt Date
- ✓ In case of rejection, specify the date and reason.
- ✓ Date and signature of the destination entity as acceptance of the waste.
- ✓ Waste treatment details.

2.1.2.3 FINAL STORAGE AT THE TREATMENT SITE and Good Practice Guidelines

Once collected, the waste is taken to an authorized treatment site where it will be stored before processing or recycling. This location must comply with all safety standards and maintain the waste under optimal conditions, avoiding exposure to external elements that could affect its quality.

INSTALLATION AREAS:

- Unloading Area
- Weighing and Reception Control Area
- Waste Storage Area

EQUIPMENT:

- Unloading and Internal Transport Equipment
- Scale

PERSONNEL:

- The personnel assigned to this facility are from the waste manager, in this case, GREEN WORLD COMPOUNDING SL.

C. GOOD PRACTICES FOR FINAL STORAGE AT THE TREATMENT SITE

- **Location**
 - Store waste in a specifically designated and clearly marked area to avoid mixing with other types of waste.
 - Keep waste in a dry, well-ventilated location, away from heat sources or direct sunlight.

- **Storage Conditions**

- The material should be kept in its original packaging, whenever possible, until treatment.
- Periodic checks of storage conditions are necessary to ensure that the waste does not degrade or become contaminated before treatment.

- **Identification and Traceability**

- All waste must be clearly identified with a batch label.
- Adhere to the implemented traceability system that allows tracking the waste from generation to final treatment. This will include a weighing and reception control activity recorded in the A2C Platform.
- Keep track of the locations of each batch using a map or location system. Logistics should follow an order that facilitates easy access to the oldest batches, ensuring these lots are the first to be removed and sent to the managing entity, thus avoiding unnecessary accumulations and optimizing the material's outflow.

- **Hygiene Conditions**

- Conduct visual inspections of the material to ensure that proper hygiene conditions are maintained. Check for the presence of unwanted contaminants.
- Containers and storage areas should be cleaned and disinfected regularly to prevent the accumulation of organic waste or contaminants.

2.2 Management of agricultural plastic mulching.

The management of agricultural mulch waste is a critical aspect of sustainable practices in the primary sector. These materials, often derived from agricultural activities, are classified as non-hazardous waste due to their composition and origin. Proper handling and management of this waste are essential to minimize environmental impact and enhance resource recovery.

This section details the procedures for managing agricultural mulch, including initial storage, collection, transportation, and final treatment. By following best practices, such as ensuring appropriate storage conditions and maintaining accurate documentation, agricultural producers can effectively manage their waste while complying with environmental regulations.

The guidelines provided here focus on maintaining the integrity of the waste material throughout its lifecycle, ensuring that it is stored in optimal conditions, transported safely, and processed efficiently. The goal is to facilitate the recovery of valuable organic substances and contribute to a circular economy in the agricultural sector.

2.2.1 IDENTIFICATION OF THE WASTE

Agricultural mulch waste comes from the activities of the primary sector. They are not classified as hazardous waste due to their composition and origin; therefore, they should be managed as non-hazardous waste.

WASTE	LER CODE	DESCRIPTION
Agricultural mulch.	02 01 04	Waste from agriculture, horticulture, aquaculture, forestry, hunting, and fishing. Plastic waste

Figure 4 Waste definition. Agricultural mulch

2.2.2 ACTIVITIES INCLUDED IN MANAGEMENT

The procedure is summarized in the following flowchart:

Figure 5. Management of Agricultural Mulch Waste. Flowchart

V*: Valorization

R12*: Pre-conditioning prior to valorization.

R3*: Recovery of organic substances not used as solvents. (demonstrator 9)

3.2.5.1 INITIAL STORAGE and Good Practice Guidelines

Initial conditioning and storage must be carried out at the facilities of the waste-generating company (generated by PROEX). In this case, since it is not a waste whose valorization treatment aims to obtain products for the food industry, the procedure is simpler.

Figure 6. Black and Natural Mulch Bales

A Guide to Good Practices for Initial Storage

- **Location**

A specific area should be designated for the storage of these wastes for easy identification.

- **Environmental Conditions**

Maintain the storage area at a moderate temperature to avoid material degradation due to extreme temperatures.

- **Material Conditioning**

The waste must be pre-conditioned before storage. It should be compacted into bales with stable weights per bundle to facilitate later handling.

- **Identification**

Since the waste producer is only responsible for storage and not handling, it is not necessary to identify the batches at this stage. Identification will be the responsibility of the waste manager upon receipt.

3.2.5.2 COLLECTION AND TRANSPORT and Good Practice Guidelines

The collection and transportation of waste must be coordinated with production cycles to avoid excessive accumulation and potential material degradation. This activity should be carried out using authorized vehicles, ensuring that the waste is not manipulated or contaminated during transport. Additionally, the transport must be accompanied by a Waste Identification Document (DI), which specifies key details such as the type of waste, producer, transporter, and responsible manager.

B. Good Practices for Collection and Transport

- **Coordination**

Establish a collection plan that aligns with production cycles to avoid waste accumulation and potential storage issues. The time limit is 6 months.

Notify the transport company in advance, indicating the quantity and type of waste to be collected for proper logistical planning.

- **Transport Conditions**

Use authorized vehicles exclusively for the transportation of waste to avoid cross-contamination.

Ensure that vehicles are clean, disinfected, and properly sealed to protect the waste from external agents. All authorized vehicles must comply and maintain a record of periodic cleaning.

Waste should be transported in the form of bales.

- **Documentation**

Accompany the transport with the appropriate documentation, including the waste identification document and records of the vehicle's cleanliness status. The format for the Waste Identification Document is registered on the A2C Platform.

The minimum information that must appear on the Waste Identification Document is as follows according to the attached model in Annex A:

- ✓ Type of waste: Hazardous; Non-hazardous
- ✓ LER Code
- ✓ Document number
- ✓ Company name of the transporter
- ✓ Company name of the origin center
- ✓ Company name of the destination
- ✓ Transporter details: Name, license plate, contact, and registration number in the transporters' registry
- ✓ Collection and reception date
- ✓ In case of rejection, specify the date and reason
- ✓ Date and signature of the destination entity as acceptance of the waste
- ✓ Waste treatment

3.2.5.3 FINAL STORAGE AT THE TREATMENT SITE and Good Practice Guidelines

Once collected, the waste is taken to an authorized treatment point where it will be stored before processing or recycling. This location must meet all safety standards and maintain the waste in optimal conditions, avoiding exposure to external elements that could affect its quality.

C. Good Practices for Final Storage at the Treatment Point

- **Location**

Store the waste in a specifically designated and clearly marked area to avoid mixing with other types of waste.

- **Storage Conditions**

The material should be kept in its original packaging whenever possible until treatment. Periodic checks of storage conditions are necessary to ensure that the waste does not degrade or become contaminated before treatment.

- **Identification and Traceability**

- All waste must be clearly identified with a batch label.

- Adhere to the implemented traceability system that allows tracking the waste from generation to final treatment. This will involve a weighing and reception control activity that will be recorded in the A2C Platform.
- It is necessary to keep track of the locations of each batch using a map or a location system. The logistics should follow an order that facilitates easy access to the oldest batches, ensuring that these lots are the first to be removed and sent to the managing entity, thus avoiding unnecessary accumulation and optimizing the material's outflow.

2.3 Management of organic agri-food waste.

2.3.1 IDENTIFICATION OF THE WASTE

The organic agri-food waste selected in the Agro2Circular project were citrus, artichoke, broccoli, cauliflower, grape and apple residues. These residues were selected on the basis of their composition (for having a high concentration of phenolic compounds of interest or fibre content) and for being predominant crops in the region of Murcia and other regions of Europe, which guarantees an adequate supply and a correct replication of the results to other regions.

The following table describes the waste that has been worked with. Information is included on the specific parts or structures that make up the waste (skins, leaves, pulp, etc.), the volume of waste generated per year in the Region of Murcia and the time at which it is generated.

Crop	Waste	Amount (tonnes/year)	Collection
Apple	Pips, skins, cores and wasted raw material	1,200	From October to December
Broccoli	Stems and whole pieces of unsuitable raw material	41,400	All the year, but especially during autumn, winter and spring
Cauliflower	Leaves and stems	3,200	Especially in winter
Citrus fruit (lemon)	Peel and pulp	200,000	All the year
Artichoke	Bracts and stems	4,400	Especially from December to May
Grape	Stems and pieces of unsuitable raw material	24,275	From late summer to early winter

In addition, the following table includes information about the company supplying each of the wastes and the volume of waste they generate per year:

Waste	Supplier	Amount (tonnes/year)
Apple	Agrotransformados (MCT) Laboratorios Almond (ALM)	350 - 400
Broccoli	ProExport (PROEXP)	33,400
Cauliflower	ProExport (PROEXP)	3,200
Lemon	Citromil (CITRO)	Pulp: 4,000 - 4,500 Peel: 30,000 - 40,000
Artichoke	ProExport (PROEXP)	3,000
Grape	Agrotransformados (MCT) Laboratorios Almond (ALM)	45 - 50

2.3.2 ACTIVITIES INCLUDED IN MANAGEMENT

The procedure is summarized in the following flowchart:

Figure 7. Management of organic agri-food waste. Flowchart.

T*: Treatment

D3: Demonstrator 3, recovery of high added value substances from agri-food waste (develop by CTNC and CITRO)

D4: Demonstrator 4, recovery of high added value substances from agri-food waste (develop by DMC)

2.3.2.1 INITIAL STORAGE and Good Practice Guidelines

Waste collection and temperature-controlled storage prior to transport must be carried out at the facilities of the company generating the waste (if it comes from raw material processing), or at the agriculture farm where the waste is generated on site at the time of harvesting or commercial distribution. The collection of organic waste must be carried out under correct sorting practices in different containers according to the plant matrix, avoiding mixing waste from different crops that may hinder the subsequent recycling process. Furthermore, storage must be carried out under optimal conditions of hygiene and control, given that we are talking about highly degradable raw materials and that the final recovery treatment is intended for application in the food industry.

INSTALLATION AREAS:

- Collection area at the end of the production lines/handling areas (field, distribution warehouses).
- Refrigerated storage area for agri-food waste

EQUIPMENT:

- Unloading and Internal Transport Equipment
- Cleaning Equipment

PERSONNEL:

- The personnel assigned to this commitment are from the waste-generating group, in this case: AGROTRANSFORMADOS (MCT), LABORATORIOS ALMOND SL (ALM), PROEXPORT(PROEXP) and CITROMIL SL (CITRO).

a. GOOD PRACTICE GUIDE FOR INITIAL STORAGE

- Collection area

The collection area must be clean, properly marked, free of contaminants and separated from other waste.

- Environmental Conditions

Keep vegetable waste at a refrigerated temperature to avoid degradation of the wastes.

Most of the waste we work with is fresh fruit and vegetables with a high degree of humidity, so we must take extreme precautions to preserve their quality and freshness, avoiding their deterioration. In addition, some of the crops are harvested during the summer months, and the high temperatures favour the process of degradation and fermentation of the fruit and vegetables.

Loss of freshness and deterioration of waste is considered a criterion for rejection of waste for recycling.

- Sorting and separation

An essential aspect of agri-food waste management is the separation of waste at source. In general, most organic waste, although generated separately because companies work in separate production campaigns, is subsequently mixed for management. Normally the waste is stored for 2-4 days (depending on the production, until the containers are full) and finally destined for animal feed (in most cases). Transport is carried out by authorised organic waste managers.

Therefore, one of the necessary actions to be carried out during the project is the separation or segregation of waste immediately after its generation in the same place where it originates.

To this end, the points of generation must be identified and provided with the necessary containers and materials to deposit them. These containers must have design and construction characteristics appropriate to the type of waste to be collected, be in good condition and be easy to clean and, if necessary, disinfect.

- **Protection and Packaging**

Waste should be stored in appropriate drums or containers, using protective and sealed covers to prevent external contamination.

Pallets should be used to elevate containers off the ground and prevent contact with moisture or dirt. This way, any leaks can be easily traced back to their source. Additionally, it is recommended to use leak retention trays.

- **Identification and Traceability**

To include the organic waste in the valorisation chain for the extraction of compounds of interest in this project, the waste is transported on the same day of its production.

Once the waste is generated, and prior to its transport to CTNC (DEMO 3) or DMC (DEMO 4), a waste identifier will be generated using the DIS tool (developed in task 1.5), to guarantee its traceability, where the following information will be included:

- ✓ Waste generating company or company of origin
- ✓ Date of generation
- ✓ Type of waste (broccoli, artichoke, grapes, etc).
- ✓ Variety of the waste (optional)
- ✓ Campaign
- ✓ Kilograms to be sent

2.3.2.2 COLLECTION AND TRANSPORT and Good Practice Guidelines

The transport of waste must be coordinated with the production cycles so that it is carried out as soon as possible and to avoid the deterioration of these fresh fruits and vegetables. This activity must be carried out with authorised vehicles, ensuring that the waste is not handled or contaminated during transport. In addition, transport must be accompanied by a Waste Identification Document (WID), which specifies key data such as the type of waste, the producer, the transporter and the responsible manager.

INSTALLATION AREAS:

- Loading Area at the waste generator's facilities
- Unloading Area at the manager's facilities

EQUIPMENT:

- Internal Transport Equipment for loading and unloading
- Authorized Vehicles

PERSONNEL:

- Transporter: personnel of the logistics company authorised for waste management.
- Loading Personnel (Generator): AGROTRANSFORMADOS (MCT), LABORATORIOS ALMOND SL (ALM), PROEXPORT (PROEXP) and CITROMIL SL (CITRO).
- Unloading Personnel (Manager): CTNC or DMC

b. GOOD PRACTICE GUIDE FOR COLLECTION AND TRANSPORT**- Coordination**

Establish a collection plan that fits in with the production cycles to ensure that the product is transferred to the CTNC/DMC facilities as quickly as possible and thus preserve the quality and properties of the product. This plan also has to be adjusted to the processing cycles of the CTNC or DMC, since once the raw material is received, it has to be processed as soon as possible to avoid loss of quality of the raw material.

Notify the transport company in advance, indicating the quantity and type of waste to be collected for proper logistical planning.

- Frequency of transport

The frequency of transport will depend entirely on the production campaigns. In this case, waste collection should take place on a daily basis, as many of the compounds of interest in agri-food waste are readily biodegradable.

- Transport conditions

Most of the waste we work with is fresh vegetable products with a high degree of humidity, so a key aspect is rapid transport from the place of generation to the place of treatment to avoid deterioration.

Ensure that vehicles are clean, disinfected and properly sealed to protect the waste from external agents. All authorized vehicles must comply with and maintain a record of regular cleaning. Waste must be transported in closed and properly labelled containers.

In addition, transport must be carried out under refrigerated conditions, especially in warm or hot months. The use of freezing processes is not recommended due to the high costs involved and the large quantities of waste that are regularly generated.

- **Documentation**

Accompany the transport with the appropriate documentation, including the Waste Identification Document and records of the vehicle's cleaning status. The format for the Waste Identification Document is included in the technological platform (DIS tool) of the A2C project.

The minimum information that must be included in the Waste Identification Document is as follows according to the attached model in Annex A:

- ✓ Type of Waste (broccoli, artichoke, grapes, etc).
- ✓ LER Code
- ✓ Document Number
- ✓ Business Name of the Transport Operator
- ✓ Business Name of the Origin Center
- ✓ Business Name of the Destination
- ✓ Transporter Details: Name, license plate number, contact information, and registration number in the transporter registry.
- ✓ Collection and Receipt Date
- ✓ In case of rejection, specify the date and reason.
- ✓ Date and signature of the destination entity as acceptance of the waste.

2.3.2.3 FINAL STORAGE AT THE TREATMENT SITE and Good Practice Guidelines

Once collected, the waste is taken to the CTNC for treatment. Once the material has been received, it is identified and labelled at the reception control. It is then weighed, a representative sample is taken for characterization (T1.4.3) and stored refrigerated for a short period of time. The waste must be conditioned and processed as soon as possible to ensure that it is in optimal condition and does not lose quality.

Figure 8. Broccoli waste reception

INSTALLATION AREAS:

- Reception Control
- Unloading Area
- Cold storage room for waste storage

EQUIPMENT:

- Unloading and Internal Transport Equipment
- Scale

PERSONNEL:

The personnel assigned to this facility are from the waste manager, in this case, CTNC or DMC

c. GOOD PRACTICE GUIDE FOR FINAL STORAGE AT THE TREATMENT SITE

- Reception of wastes

Once the waste arrives at the CTNC or DMC facilities, it will go through reception control, where it will be identified and labelled for storage control. It will also be weighed and transported using wheeled containers, pallet trucks or forklifts to the area designated for storage (cold storage) and/or processing.

- Storage time

It is important that waste is stored for a short period of time, since due to its highwater content, it is highly putrescent and highly biodegradable and can undergo rapid fermentation processes, even under refrigeration conditions.

Therefore, waste must be processed in the shortest possible time. In case this is not possible, or even to avoid deterioration even if rapid processing is foreseen, it is advisable to carry out the necessary pretreatments to facilitate its storage under optimal hygienic and safety conditions. These pretreatments can also favor the following steps in the extraction process of compounds of interest. The pretreatments carried out are drying (especially when processing is not going to be immediate, as it allows to extend the storage time without loss of quality), decanting (especially in cases where the waste has high humidity and water leaks occur during storage at source and transport), grinding, crushing (both physical pretreatments allow the waste to be homogenized and favor the subsequent extraction stage), among others.

Figure 9. Lemon waste dried in climatic chamber

- Storage conditions

The storage conditions (cooling temperature, humidity, etc.) should be checked regularly to ensure that the waste is not degraded or contaminated before treatment (especially by microbiological growth). In addition, proper hygienic conditions should

be maintained. Containers and storage areas should be regularly cleaned and disinfected.

- **Identification and traceability**

All waste must be clearly identified with a batch label.

Adhere to the traceability system in place that allows waste to be tracked from generation to final treatment. This will include a weighing and reception control activity recorded in the A2C Platform.

3 Conclusions

In the case of multilayer aseptic packaging, the need to maintain optimal hygiene and control conditions is emphasized, given that this waste can be valorized for applications in the food industry. For agricultural mulch waste, although the process is simpler, proper planning and monitoring are also stressed to maximize its recovery and quality, which is reflected in the final product.

Both processes heavily rely on traceability and documentation systems, such as the A2C platform, to ensure that the flow of materials from generation to treatment is controlled and efficient, guaranteeing perfect product traceability. Ultimately, these practices not only minimize environmental impact but also contribute to a circular economy through the recovery and valorization of these wastes.

The management of agri-food organic waste, due to its composition (high water content), must be carried out efficiently in short periods of time and taking care at all times of the storage and transport conditions to avoid contamination or deterioration. Good logistical coordination and an adequate identification and traceability system are key elements to successfully carry out this process. Special attention must be paid to critical points in the process such as the proper separation and classification of waste in the generating companies (artichoke, broccoli, citrus fruits, etc.), or temperature control to avoid decomposition. Finally, correct hygienic conditions must be guaranteed, since the final recovery treatment is intended for use in the food industry.

5. ANNEXES

5.1 Annex A. Waste Identification Document

GOBIERNO DE ESPAÑA		MINISTERIO PARA LA TRANSICIÓN ECOLÓGICA Y EL RETO DEMOGRÁFICO	
DOCUMENTO DE IDENTIFICACIÓN DE RESIDUOS SIN NOTIFICACIÓN PREVIA			
(Artículo 6.1 y Anexo III del R.D. 553/2020, de 2 de junio, por el que se regula el traslado de residuos en el interior del territorio del Estado. B.O.E. nº 171 del 19/07/2020)			
Documento de Identificación nº ¹			
Fecha inicio de traslado ²			
INFORMACIÓN RELATIVA AL OPERADOR DEL TRASLADO			
NIF	Razón social/Nombre		
NIMA ³	Nº inscripción ³	Tipo Operador Traslado ⁴	
Dirección			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		
Firma operador de traslado			
INFORMACIÓN RELATIVA AL ORIGEN DEL TRASLADO			
Información del centro productor o poseedor de residuos o de la instalación origen del traslado:			
NIF ⁵	Razón social/Nombre		
NIMA ³	Nº inscripción ³	Tipo centro Productor ⁶	
Dirección ⁷			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		
Información de la empresa autorizada para realizar operaciones de tratamiento de residuos, incluido el almacenamiento, en caso de que el origen del traslado sea una instalación de tratamiento de residuos			
NIF	Razón social/Nombre		
NIMA	Nº inscripción		
Dirección			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		
INFORMACIÓN RELATIVA AL DESTINO DEL TRASLADO			
Información de la instalación de destino¹⁵			
NIF	Razón social/Nombre		
NIMA	Nº inscripción	Tipo centro gestor ⁸	
Dirección			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		
Información de la empresa autorizada para realizar operaciones de tratamiento de residuos, incluido el almacenamiento, en la instalación de destino			
NIF	Razón social/Nombre		
NIMA	Nº inscripción		
Dirección			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		

Figure 10. Page1/2 Waste Identification Document

INFORMACIÓN SOBRE EL RESIDUO QUE SE TRASLADA			
Código LER/LER- extendido ⁹			
Descripción del residuo:			
Operación de tratamiento destino (código R) ¹⁰		Código operación tratamiento destino desagregado (4 cifras) ¹¹	
Descripción operación tratamiento ¹²			
Cantidad (kg netos)			

INFORMACIÓN DEL SISTEMA DE RESPONSABILIDAD AMPLIADA DEL PRODUCTOR QUE, EN SU CASO, DECIDE LA INSTALACIÓN			
NIF	Razón social/Nombre		
NIMA	Nº inscripción		
Dirección			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		

INFORMACIÓN RELATIVA AL TRANSPORTISTA			
N.I.F.:	Razón social/Nombre y apellidos		
NIMA:	Nº inscripción		
Dirección			C.P.
Municipio	Provincia		
Teléfono	Correo electrónico		

INFORMACIÓN SOBRE LA ACEPTACIÓN DEL RESIDUO			
Fecha entrega:	Kg. netos recibidos	Aceptación	Sí <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Fecha aceptación/rechazo			
Acción en caso de rechazo			
Fecha devolución/reenvío			
Motivo de rechazo			
Firma del gestor de la instalación de destino recepción del residuo ¹³			
Firma del gestor de la instalación de destino aceptación/rechazo residuo ¹⁴			

INFORMACIÓN SOBRE LA RECEPCIÓN EN ORIGEN DEL RESIDUO RECHAZADO Y DEVUELTO			
Fecha entrega:	Kg. netos recibidos		

Figure 11. Page 2/2 Waste Identification Document

